

Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel Using *Carica* *Papaya* Leaves Extract

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ABSTRACT

Gravimetric methods were used to test the ability of Carica papaya leaves extract (CPLE) on corrosion inhibition of mild steel in 1M HCl acidic solution. The temperature of the reaction, the concentration of the extract, and the length of immersion were changed during the experiments. According to the weight loss method's results, mild steel corrodes less quickly as extract concentration rises while inhibition efficiency also rises with increase in extract concentration. 90.02% was the maximum inhibitory efficiency for CPLE at 1.0g/L that was noted. Studies on temperature showed that inhibition efficiency increased with decrease in temperature and that, in contrast to unrestrained solutions, activation energies decreased in inhibited solutions. For the purpose of inhibiting behavior, a mechanism of physical adsorption of the plant components on the metal surface is proposed. Thermodynamic and kinetic parameters were computed and examined. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm was followed by the CPLE's adsorption on the mild steel surface. According to SEM-EDX data, CPLE delayed the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M HCl by forming an adsorption coating on the surface.

Keywords: Corrosion, Gravimetric, Inhibition, Carica papaya, Thermodynamics, Kinetics, Mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Although corrosion has been called by many names, the word itself is as old as the earth. It is usually referred to as rust, and it shortens an object's life span while destroying its shine and attractiveness (Devarayan K.,1. et al., 2012). On the other hand, corrosion is a naturally occurring phenomenon that is generally understood to be the deterioration or disintegration of metal surfaces due to chemical reactions between the metal and the surrounding environment (Ayssar N., et al., 2010). Reversing the process of extractive metallurgy, it helps to restore metals to their ore.

Usually, the corroding metal acts as a tiny electrochemical cell during this electrochemical process. The growing industrial use of acid media has made the study of mild steel corrosion processes more significant in acidic solutions (Buchweishaija J., 2011). In the industrial sector, acid solutions are frequently used to remove unwanted scale and rust from metal finishes. Heat exchangers, industrial acid cleaning, and acid pickling are the three main application areas. One of the most effective methods for controlling metal corrosion is the use of inhibitors, particularly in acidic solutions to avoid unexpected metal dissolution and acid consumption (Bhuvaneswari, T.K. et al., 2018). Scientists are working together to develop appropriate compounds that might be utilized as anti-corrosion in various media to keep the metal from deteriorating, in the meantime, in an effort to extend the life of metallic and alloy materials. Up to 3.5% of the country's GDP may be lost annually in India owing to corrosion, and the annual cost of corrosion-related expenses is estimated to be over Rs 2.0 lakh crores (Saratha R. and Vasudha V. G., 2009). Costs associated with corrosion show up as early failure or deterioration that calls for upkeep and part replacement. The projected annual total direct cost of corrosion in the United States alone is over \$300 billion, or 3.2% of GDP. It was indicated that 25 to 30 percent of this whole cost might be reduced if corrosion optimum management strategies are implemented (Bhuvaneswari, T.K., et al, 2018 ; Saratha R. and Vasudha V. G., 2009). Apart from the loss of materials, corrosion poses a risk to the environment, interferes with industrial processes, and endangers human safety. It is crucial to find a means of managing or stopping corrosion in addition to being timely. The key to reducing corrosion failures is being aware of corrosion and implementing timely, effective management measures. If corrosion is stopped in the interim, the enormous sum of money that would have been lost to it could be put toward building new roads and jobs, for example. Given this, corrosion is an unwanted phenomenon that needs to be stopped. An inhibitor of corrosion is a chemical compound that,

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when added in small quantities to a liquid or gas, reduces the rate at which a material, usually an alloy or metal, corrodes (Okhio C. and Adams M., 2012)6). Amid other preventive corrosion techniques, synthetic chemicals derived from organic and inorganic substances have been employed as inhibitors to address the issue of metal corrosion in recent years (Stango, S.A; Vijayalakshmi, U., 2018)). Due to their harmful consequences, the majority of these synthetic chemical inhibitors are regrettably costly and not environmentally friendly (Salami L. et al., 2012), as an inhibitor's ability to protect the environment must be taken into account before it can be used. Because natural resources are widely accessible, inexpensive, renewable, have inherent biodegradability, and are agreeable to the environment friendly, they are seen as desired as an excellent source for this reason (Ostovari A.H et al., 2009). Furthermore, through chemical transformation, natural resources produce flexible materials with a wide range of uses in corrosion resistance against different corrodents (Handa S.S., et al., 2008). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine whether extract from *Carica papaya* leave may prevent mild steel from corroding in an acidic environment.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS AND MATERIALS

Materials

The *carica papaya* leaves used in this study were obtained in the vicinity of Federal Polytechnic Ado, Ekiti State, Nigeria and were authenticated at the Department of Biology, Bamidele Olumilua, University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The mild steel employed for this study was procured and the chemical composition was determined at Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Chemicals and solutions

Chemicals that were used in this study were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. Hydrochloric acid, HCl, 38%, product No. 351280-500, ethanol and nitrogen gas. Corrosive solutions (electrolytes) were prepared by diluting concentrated acids (1.0M) to a required concentration by deionized water.

The aggressive acidic solution of 1.0 M HCl was prepared by dilution of concentrated HCl with distilled water and all experiment was carried out in unstirred solutions and all weighing was made using analytical weighing balance (Metler Toledo PB153). Other materials and equipment used include rotary evaporator, distilled water, nitrogen gas, beaker, measuring cylinder, thermostated water bath, thermometer, paper tape, whatman filter paper, desiccator.

Preparation of plant sample

The *Carica papaya* were washed and dried at room temperature, ground and sieved through a 850 μ m. The samples were later extracted with Ethanol by Maceration method (Handa S.S et al., 2008). After three days, the mixture was pressed by filtration through a 0.25 μ m and the filtrate obtained was put in a vacuum rotary evaporator at a temperature of 60⁰ C to obtain the *carica papaya* concentrate. The crude extract obtained was used to prepare test solutions at concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6., 0.8 and 1.0g/L

Mild steel preparation

The sheets were physically pressed and cut into coupons of 2.5 × 2.5 × 0.4 cm. To suspend the coupons in the corrosive liquid, a 5mm diameter hole was cut near the upper edge. Glass hooks

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were then used to hold them in place. The mild steel was polished with a struer polishing machine using various grades of emery paper, then washed with distilled water, dried with nitrogen gas, and stored in moisture-free desiccators before use (Oguzie E.E.,2005; Okafor, P.C. et al., 2007).

Weight loss Experiments

In weight loss experiment, a previously weighted metal coupon was completely immersed in 100 ml of 1.0 M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentration (0.2g, 0.4g, 0.6g, 0.8g and 1.0g) of the ethanol extracts of CPLE with the aid of glass hooks for four hours. After every 4 hours, each coupon was withdrawn from the test solution, and the corrosion product was removed by washing each coupon in distilled water, rinsed in acetone and dried completely using nitrogen gas before re-weighing. From the initial and final weights of the mild steel, the weight loss, corrosion rate (CR ,g hr⁻¹ cm⁻²) in absence and presence of extract, the inhibition efficiency (I.E %) of the extract and the degree of surface coverage were calculated using equations i, ii and iii respectively (Eddy N.O.,2009)..

$$CR = \frac{\Delta W}{AT} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$IE = 1 - \frac{CR_2}{CR_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$Surface\ Coverage\ (\theta) = 1 - \left(\frac{CR_2}{CR_1}\right) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where Δw is the weight loss in grammes, CR_1 and CR_2 are the corrosion rates of the mild steel strip coupons in absence and presence of inhibitor, A is the cross-sectional area in cm² and t

is the exposure time in hours. The experiment was repeated by varying the temperature of the acidic medium and days of immersion of the mild steel in acidic medium.

RESULTS AND DISCURSION

Effect of extract concentration on corrosion rates of mild steel

Figure 1 illustrates how mild steel corroded more slowly in 1M HCL as the extract content of *Carica papaya* increased. This suggests that the amount of inhibitor present affects how quickly mild steel corrodes in acid solutions, and that the inhibitor's presence in the acid solution contributed to the mild steel's corrosion rate decrease. This can be clarified further by pointing out that as the extract concentration rises, more of the extract's phytochemical ingredients adsorbed on the mild steel surface. This creates a barrier for mass transfer, which stops the corrosion from spreading. This outcome demonstrated that the capacity of the extract's to protect the mild steel from corrosion is concentration-dependent, which aligned with research of the previous researchers (Raja P. B. and Sethuraman M. G. 2008; Riggs O. L. 1973; Quraishi M. A. et al., 2009).

Figure 1: Effect of concentration of CPLE on the corrosion rate of mild steel in 1M HCl.

Effect of Extract Inhibition Efficiency on mild steel

Figure 2 makes it clear that an increase in extract concentration corresponds with an increase in inhibitory efficiency. This might be the result of the extract's organic components adhering to the mild steel's surface, blocking the reaction sites and shielding the metal from additional ion attack from the corrosive medium. Previous research has demonstrated that higher extract molecule adsorption on the metal surface can account for an increase in inhibition efficacy with an increase in inhibitor concentration (Okafor P. C. et al., 2005). This suggests that the extract's ability to inhibit aggressive ions is enhanced when the degree of metal surface coverage by adsorbed inhibitor species in acid solution increases. This decreases the surface area that the extract's aggressive ions can attack.

Figure 2: Effect of concentration of CPLE on its inhibition efficiency.

Effect of Temperature on Corrosion rate.

At temperatures ranging from 303 to 333K, the impact of temperature on the rate of mild steel corrosion in the presence and absence of different concentrations of CPLE in 1M HCl solution was investigated. Based on the findings displayed in Figure 3, mild steel corrodes more quickly at higher temperatures both without and the one with varying concentration of CPLE. This is to be expected since a rise in temperature raises the average kinetic energy of the molecules interacting which thereby increasing the rate at which mild steel corrodes. Nonetheless, the Figure 3 shows that the mild steel corrosion rate in the controlled acid solution is significantly lower than the corrosion rate in the unrestrained acid solution. This makes sense as the inhibitors' ability to reduce the pace at which mild steel corrodes is demonstrated by the inhibited acid solution's declining corrosion rate (Atkinson J. T. N. and Van Droffelaar H.,**1995**).

Figure 3: Effect of Corrosion Rate of mild steel coupons in 1M HCl at different temperature in the absence and presence of different concentration of CPLE.

Effect of Temperature on Inhibition Efficiency

The consequence of temperature on inhibition efficiency was examined at different concentrations of the extracts and the results are presented in Figures 4. From the results, it was revealed that the inhibition efficiency of the extracts was decreasing with increase in temperature of the acidic media. The decrease in the inhibition efficiency of the extracts with increase in temperature might due to an increase in the average kinetic energy which led to the partial desorption of the extracts from metal surfaces [Blaedel W. J, and Meloche WV. 1963]. This phenomenon is consistent with the mechanism of physical adsorption. (Eddy N.O., 2009; Ebenso, E.E. 2003; Ebenso E. E., 2004).

Figure 4: Plot of inhibition efficiency of CPLE against temperature at varying concentrations

Effect of immersion time on weight loss of mild steel

The effects of immersion time on mild steel weight loss in 1.0 M HCl was evaluated in the absence and presence of different concentrations of CPLE extract (0.2 - 1.0 g/L) for a period of 7 days at room temperature. Figures 5 show weight loss - time curve for mild steel in 1 M HCl in the presence and absence of different concentrations of the extracts. It is observed from the curves that the amount of material loss decreases greatly in the presence of the extracts compared to that in the blank acid solution and it was also observed to be dependent on the concentration of the extracts which is an indication that the extracts inhibit the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution. The presence of the the CPLE as inhibitors reduced the weight loss as much as possible. There was a greater weight loss as the time increases in the acidic medium. The decrease in the weight of the mild steel in the presence of the plant extracts can be ascribed to the adsorption of phytochemical constituents present in the extracts (Saratha R. and Vaduadha V. G. 2010). Regardless of the extract concentration the highest value of weight loss was recorded on the day seven of the experiment.

**Figure 5: Plot of weight loss against time for corrosion of mild steel in 1.0 M HCl
in the absence and presence of different concentration CPLE.**

Kinetic Studies

By fitting the corrosion data into several rate laws, the kinetics of mild steel corrosion in 1M HCl with and without varying extract concentrations were investigated at room temperature. The current investigation designates the weight of the mild steel coupon at time 't' as 'W₁,' the end weight as 'W₂,' the weight loss after time 't' as ΔW , and the weight of the metal after time t as (W_i - ΔW). Plotting $\ln (W_i - \Delta W)$ versus time using equation (4), as illustrated in Figure 6, revealed a linear variation that validates first order reaction kinetics for mild steel corrosion in 1M HCl solutions with and without CPLE. As shown in Table 1, the linearity of the curves in the inhibited and uninhibited solutions suggests that its presence greatly lowers the corrosion reaction's rate constant without altering the corrosion reaction's kinetics.

Figure 6: Variation of $\ln (W_i - \Delta W)$ against time (days) for mild steel coupons in 1M HCl solution containing CPLE.

The half-lives were computed using equation 5, and the rate constants were inferred from the graph's slope as depicted in Figure 6.

$$\ln (W_i - \Delta W) = -k_1t + \ln W_i \dots\dots\dots 4$$

$$t_{1/2} = 0.693/k \dots\dots\dots 5$$

Table 1 lists the estimated values for the rate constant and half-life at various extract concentrations.

The half-life of the metal increases with extract concentration, indicating that the extract's inhibitory effectiveness improves with extract concentration. This gives support for the previous claim that the mild steel's corrosion rate falls with increasing extract content, leading to increased inhibition efficiency (Stephen G.Y. et al., 2004).

Table 1. The calculated values of rate constant, k and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of the corrosion reactions for mild steel in 1M HCl solution in the absence and presence CPLE

Conc.	Blank	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Rate constant (day^{-1})	0.0276	0.0138	0.0092	0.0069	0.0046	0.0023
Half-life (days)	25.1	50.2	75.3	100.4	150.7	301.3

Thermodynamic Evaluation

To determine the steadiness of the adsorbed layer film of the extract on mild steel and the temperature dependence of corrosion of steel in 1.0 M HCl, weight loss measurements were carried out at temperature between 303 K – 323 K with and without the samples extract at concentration range of 0.2 to 1.0 g/L for an immersion time of 4 hours. The thermodynamic parameters such as Activation Energy (E_a), Enthalpy (ΔH°) and Entropy (ΔS) change of activation on the mild steel corrosion rate at the varying temperature were studied in order to ascertain the mechanism of adsorption process involved. The energy of activation was evaluated from the effect of temperature on the mild steel corrosion rate in 1.0 M HCl using Arrhenius equation:

$$\text{Log}(\text{CR}) = \text{Log}A - \frac{E_a}{2.303RT} \dots\dots\dots 7$$

Where CR is the corrosion rate, E_a is the activation energy, R is the gas constant and T is the temperature.

A plot of log CR against the inverse of temperature ($1/T$) gives a straight line graph with negative slopes of $-\frac{E_a}{2.303R}$ as shown in Figures 7a.

The enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) change of the samples extract were calculated from the effect of temperature on the corrosion rate of mild steel in 1.0 M HCl using Eyring Transition state equation.

$$\text{CR} = \left[\frac{RT}{Nh} \right] \exp \left[\frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} \right] \exp \left[\frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{RT} \right] \dots\dots\dots 8$$

Where CR is the corrosion rate at temperature T, R is the molar gas constant, n is Avogadro's constant, and h is the Plank's constant. A plot of $\log (CR/T)$ vs $1/T$ is a straight-line graph (Figure 7b) from which the enthalpy and entropy change was obtained from the slope ($-\Delta H/2.303R$) and intercept ($\log (R/nh) + \Delta S/2.303R$) of the graph respectively.

Figure 7a: Arrhenius plot for the mild steel in 1.0 M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations CPLE extract.

Figure7b: Transition State plot for the mild steel in 1.0 M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of CPLE.

Careful examination of Table 2 reveals that the values of activation energy (E_a) in blank solution is 7.16 kJ/mol, and values increases to 18.62 KJ/mol in the presence of the extract which shows that the adsorbed organic matter has provided a physical barrier to charge and mass transfer, leading to reduction in corrosion rate (Ebenso, E.E., 2003; Abiola O.K. and Oforka N.C. (2002) . Also as observed from Table 2, the values of E_a increased as their concentrations increases from 0.2 g/L to 1.0 g/L and all the E_a values in the range of the studied concentration were higher than that of the uninhibited solution. Earlier investigators have established that the value of $E_a > 80$ kJmol⁻¹ indicates chemical adsorption whereas $E_a < 80$ kJmol⁻¹ infers physical adsorption (Vijayalakshmi P.R., et al., 2011). In the present study, a physical adsorption mechanism is proposed since the values of E_a are lower than 80 kJmol⁻¹. The increase in activation energy of the inhibited acidic solution indicates the deactivation of the acid molecules on collision with the metal surface by the introduction of the extract thus reducing the rate of acid attack on the metals. Previous researchers have demonstrated that the value of E_a increases with increase in concentrations on various plants (Quraishi M. A.,et al.,2009; Mayanglambam R.S.,2011; Shivakumar S.S. and Mohana K.N.S.,2012; Cang H., et. al.,2012).

The values of enthalpy (ΔH°) change calculated for the CPLE extracts are positive and it increases with an increase in extracts concentration. The positive values of the enthalpy change showed that the adsorption of the extracts on the surface of mild steel revealed an endothermic reaction; while an increase in the enthalpy change values with increase in concentration indicates that the addition of the extracts slows down the corrosion process and additional energy is needed for it to break the film barrier and react with mild steel surface. Furthermore, the entropy change values obtained are all negatives, which indicated that there is a higher association i.e there was a decrease in the

rate of disorderliness of the system as a result of the adsorption of extract on the surface of the mild steel (Mohan D., 2012).

Table 2: Activation parameters for mild steel corrosion rate in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of CPLE.

Concentrations	Blanks	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Ea (Kj/mol.)	7.16	12.30	14.33	14.49	14.50	18.62
ΔH (kJ/mol)	4.53	9.68	10.70	11.55	11.87	15.98
ΔS (kJ/mol K)	-126721	-11.7001	-12.0981	-12.7121	-12.3401	-11.6651

Adsorption Isotherms

Based on the inhibitor's adsorption properties, the nature of the inhibitor-corroding surface contact during metal corrosion inhibition has been inferred. The adsorption of the plant extract's constituent parts on the metal surface can account for the suppression of mild steel corrosion in acidic solution upon the addition of different amounts of the extract (Ating E.I.,2010). The proportion of the surface covered by the adsorption molecule (θ) is directly related to the mild steel's percentage inhibitory efficiency (I.E%). As a result, the adsorption isotherm offers crucial hints concerning the connection between the concentration of extract in solution and the surface of the metal coated with the adsorbed species. In this study two adsorption isotherms were used; Langmuir and Frenlich adsorption isotherm.

Langmuir adsorption isotherm shows a correlation between the surface coverage (θ) and the inhibitor concentration (C) in an electrolyte as follows:

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K_{ads}} + C \dots \dots \dots 9$$

where K_{ads} is the adsorption constant, C is the inhibitor concentration and θ is the surface coverage. When $\frac{C}{\theta}$ is plotted against C, a straight line graphs were obtained. K_{ads} can be calculated from the intercept of the straight lines. The values obtained for extract are presented in Table 3. The results show that the slopes and regression coefficients are very close to unity indicating that the adsorption of the inhibitor on the surface of mild steel is consistent with Langmuir isotherm. The value of the adsorption constant (K_{ads}) decreases with increase in temperature showing that the molecules of the inhibitors were physically adsorbed on the mild steel surfaces.

Figure 8: Langmuir adsorption Isotherm for the mild steel in 1.0 M HCl for of CPLE at different temperatures.

Table 3: Calculated Parameters from Langmuir isotherm of CPLE

Temp.(K)	Slope	K _{ads} (g/L)	r ²
303	1.058	16.01	0.997
313	1.095	14.70	0.995
323	1.131	14.16	0.997
333	1.161	13.70	0.998

The intercept obtained from the graph was related to inverse of equilibrium adsorption constant (K_{ads}) in Equation 10 which is related to the Gibbs free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) as employed by the previous investigators (Olasehinde, E.F., et al., 2015).

$$K_{ads} = \frac{1}{55.5} \exp \left[\frac{-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}}{RT} \right] \dots\dots\dots 10$$

This equation can also be expressed as:

$$\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ} = -2.303RT \text{ Log } (55.5K_{ads}) \dots\dots\dots 11$$

Where, ΔG_{ads}^o is the Gibbs free energy of adsorption, K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant for the adsorption phenomenon, R is the universal gas constant, T is the thermodynamic temperature (kelvin) and the value of 55.5 is the molar concentration of water in solution.

Equation (11) was used to compute the Gibbs free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) for the CPLE in 1M HCl solution. Table 4 displays the computed values for K_{ads} and ΔG_{ads}.

Table 4: The values of equilibrium adsorption constant and Gibbs free energy of adsorption for mild steel corrosion in 1M HCL at different temperatures

Temperature (K)	303	313	323	333
Kads (g L ⁻¹)	16.01	14.70	14.16	13.70
ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-17.11	-17.45	17.91	18.37

From table 4, the values of ΔG_{ads} were negative in all the temperature studied. This indicates the spontaneous adsorption of extracts on surface of mild steel in HCl acid solution. The spontaneity of adsorption process and the stability of adsorbed layer on the surface of mild steel was depicted by the negative values of Gibb's free energy (Shukla Sudhish K., et al., 2011), and that the extracts are strongly adsorbed on the medium mild steel surface by physical adsorption mechanism (Ebenso, E.E. ,2003). Previous researchers have established that the values of ΔG°_{ads} up to -20 kJmol⁻¹ are consistent with electrostatic interaction between charged molecules and a charged metal indicating physisorption, while those more negative than -40 kJmol⁻¹ involve charge sharing or transfer from the inhibitor molecules to the metal surface to form a co-ordinate type of bond otherwise known as chemisorption (Ebenso, E.E. 2003; Voudrias E., et al., 2002). In the present study, the values of ΔG°_{ads} are less than -40 kJ mol⁻¹ which indicate that the adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface confirms a physical adsorption mechanism (Vimala, J. R., et al., 2011).

Freundlich isotherm

This adsorption isotherm is commonly used to describe the adsorption characteristics for the heterogeneous surface. The equation is

$$\theta = K_f C^{1/n} \dots\dots\dots 12$$

Where K_f is the Freundlich isotherm constant, n is the adsorption intensity, C is the concentration of the inhibitor and θ is the surface coverage. Linearization of the above equation gives

$$\text{Log } \theta = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C \dots\dots\dots 13$$

The plots of the logarithm of the surface coverage (θ) against inhibitor concentration at different temperatures are shown in Figures 9 while Table 5 showed the values of the slope ($1/n$), intercept $\log K_f$ together with their correlation coefficients (r^2). Constant K_f is an approximate indicator of adsorption capacity and $1/n$ is a function of the strength of adsorption in the process of adsorption [33]. Report from past researchers indicated that $1/n$ can be > 1 or < 1 . If it is 1, then the partition between the phases are independent of concentration. If it is below 1, it indicates a normal adsorption but if $1/n > 1$, it indicates cooperative adsorption (Mohan S. and Karthikeyan J.,1997). In the present study the values of k_f and $1/n$ for both extracts are less than 1 indicating that adsorption of phytochemical constituents of the extracts on mild steel is a normal adsorption process and is depended on concentration of the extracts. The correlation coefficient (r^2) of the extract ranges from 0.958 – 0.975.

Figure 9: Freundlich adsorption Isotherm for the mild steel in 1.0 M HCl for extract of CPLE at different temperatures.

Table 5: Calculated Parameters from Freundlich isotherm for extracts of CPLE

Temp. (K)	r^2	1/n	K_f (L/mg)
303	0.958	0.111	0.8851
313	0.863	0.096	0.8492
323	0.966	0.104	0.8318
333	0.975	0.110	0.8110

Surface Morphology

With a scanning electron microscope (SEM), the surface morphology of mild steel was investigated following a 72-hour immersion in a 1M HCl solution, both in the presence and absence of CPLE, to verify the degree of surface modification. Figures 11a, b, and c display the SEM micrographs, respectively. With a smooth and fine surface,

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Figure 10a: SEM image of mild steel not immersed in acidic solution.

Figure 10b: SEM image of mild steel treated in immersed in an uninhibited acidic solution.

Figure 10c: SEM image of mild steel immersed in acidic solution containing 1.0g/L of CPLE.

Figure 10a SEM image of mild steel before it was immersed in an acidic solution reveals that the steel has not been harmed by an aggressive attack. The SEM picture of mild steel following

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immersion in a 1M HCl solution without the extract are displayed in Figure 10b. The photograph makes it evident that the lack of extract inhibitor in the acid media caused significant damage to the mild steel surface, leaving it rough and full of pits. Figure 10c shows the SEM picture of mild steel immersed in a 1M HCl solution containing 1.0 gL⁻¹ of the extract. It is noted that the mild steel's surface exhibits minimal acid corrosion result. A homogeneous, thick layer covers the surface, possibly as a result of CPLE molecules adhering to the mild steel's surface. This layer effectively prevents mild steel from corroding.

Conclusion

CPLE is an efficient green inhibitor of mild steel corrosion in 1 M HCl. The extract's inhibition efficiency improves with its concentration but decrease with increase in temperature. Corrosion inhibition is done primarily by the physical adsorption of various chemicals in the extract onto the mild steel surface. The adsorption of CPLE on the surface of mild steel in 1M HCl follows the Langmuir adsorption isotherm and is a spontaneous, exothermic reaction accompanied by a drop in entropy. The reaction's kinetics are first order, and the metal half-lives increase as the extract concentration increases. SEM-EDX confirms that CPLE retards the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M HCl by forming an adsorption coating on the surface.

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